

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Summer is usually a quiet time. However, J.UCS seems to be fairly well established by now, since papers keep coming in at about the same rate.

This issue contains four papers from four very different areas: I hope you will enjoy reading them! Don't forget to encourage colleagues to submit papers to J.UCS once in a while. Springer has just printed new brochures about J.UCS, so if you need some for yourself or for friends just drop me a note and I can send you a few.

Best wishes for the rest of the summer,

cordially

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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